
Space Shuttle Ku-Band Radar

**Chau T. Pham
Alicia L. Leonard
Lyndon B. Johnson Space Center
Houston, Texas 77058**

Abstract

The Shuttle Ku-Band system is a dual mode system that can be operated either as a two-way communications with the ground via the Tracking and Data Relay Satellite System or as a radar system to track another spacecraft. The radar mode is used during rendezvous and proximity operations to provide range, range rate, angle, and angle rate information to the on-board Shuttle navigation system. Target detection at short range can be determined from any single transmitted pulse that crosses the required threshold whereas at long range, detection is based upon the integration of all the transmitted pulses from a complete data cycle. Once a target is detected, the radar is switched to the track mode and performs range, range rate, and/or angle tracking. This paper discusses the concepts and techniques utilized in the search and track modes, including a description of the waveforms and how signal processing is performed.

Introduction

The Ku-Band radar is designed to provide accurate target information to assist the crew in maneuvering the Shuttle to the target safely and efficiently. Predicted target location is generally supplied by the Shuttle General Purpose Computer (GPC) to point the antenna in the vicinity of the target and a search is performed to acquire the target. Capability to perform a spiral scan is available to accurately determine the angular position of the target relative to the antenna boresight axis. During the search, either single pulse detection (SPD) mode or constant false alarm rate (CFAR) will be employed depending on the designated range. In the SPD mode, the return signal from the sum channel is sampled and digitized before comparing to a predetermined threshold and a detection is declared when the magnitude of any data sample exceeds that threshold. For CFAR which is used at longer range, detection will involve range gate setting and doppler filtering. The signal processing for CFAR is more complicated than in SPD but the doppler frequency can be extracted to determine the target's velocity. In addition, digital gain resulted from integration of all the successive pulses in a data cycle will reduce the required signal-to-noise ratio. Upon target acquisition, radar automatically switches to the track mode where both signals from the sum channel as well as from the difference channel are processed to derive three discriminant signals known as the sum, alpha, and beta error signals. These signals provide the position and velocity errors between the actual and the predicted measurements and thus, when fed back to the tracking loop, allow the radar to adjust its measurements properly and update its new estimates for the next measurements.

Ku-Band Radar Descriptions and Specifications

The Ku-Band system is designed to utilize many electronic and mechanical components for both communications and radar modes [1]. The antenna, the servo system and some transmitter/receiver circuits are shared by both modes. The system is comprised of four line replaceable units (LRUs), namely the Deployed Assembly (DA), Electronics Assembly 1 (EA-1), Electronics Assembly 2 (EA-2), and Signal Processor Assembly (SPA). The DA consists of the antenna, gimbals, mounting structure, and radio frequency electronics. The EA-1 controls the antenna and all radar/comm interfaces with the Shuttle. The EA-2 and the SPA perform signal processing for the radar and communications modes, respectively. Figure 1 shows a block diagram of the Ku-Band system LRUs and their functions.

Figure 1. Ku-Band system LRU's and their functions.

Other radar design features include multiple frequencies, pulse repetition frequencies (PRFs) and pulse widths. The Shuttle Ku-Band radar transmitter is cycled through five different frequencies that are spaced 51 MHz apart. Two sets of PRFs are included for different range operations. A high PRF of 6970 Hz is used for ranges less than 7.2 nm and a low PRF of 2987 Hz is for ranges greater than 7.2 nm. The lower PRF is used at the long ranges to provide a maximum unambiguous range (27.1 nm). The higher PRF provides a wider range of doppler frequencies resulting in no range rate ambiguities at the shorter ranges.

The Ku-Band radar is specified to provide range, range rate and angular information with accuracies requirements listed in Table 1. The radar can acquire and track a target with radar cross section equivalent to 1 square meter at a range of 10 nautical miles. Range to the target is determined by electronically measuring the elapsed time from a pulse transmitted by the radar to the return pulse that was reflected back from an object. Doppler offset, the change in the received and transmitted frequencies, is detected to determine the target's velocity. A 5-slot feed network is employed for angle tracking which senses the direction of the target with respect to the boresight of the antenna. This technique is known as monopulse tracking and allows the antenna to point and track the target continuously.

Table 1. - Accuracy Specifications and Limits

Specification	Range	Range Rate	Angle
Coverage	Minimum: 100 ft. Maximum: 25.5 n.mi.	Decreasing range: 0 to 148 ft/s Increasing range: 0 to 75 ft/s	Maximum diameter: 60°
Accuracy (3-sigma)	80 ft or 1 percent	1 ft/s	8 mrad (0.46°)
Data Resolution	0.3 ft	0.05 ft/s	0.09°

Radar Operation Modes

The Ku-Band system provides four antenna steering modes for searching and tracking a target. They are GPC Acquisition (GPC Acq), GPC Designate (GPC Des), Auto, and Manual. In GPC Acq, the initial antenna position is provided by the Shuttle GPC from the on-board navigation data. The radar is configured to search the target about that initial position with a spiral scan. Once the target is acquired, the antenna will continually track and follow the target and provide range, range rate, angle, and angle rate information. The antenna will automatically perform a search if the system breaks track while tracking in this mode. In GPC Des, target position is also provided by the computer but the antenna does not perform spiral scan search. A range search is enabled and when a detection is confirmed, the radar will range track the target and provide range and range rate information; angle designates are provided by the Shuttle GPC to maintain antenna line of sight to the target. Operations of Auto and Manual modes are similar to GPC Acq and GPC Des except that the antenna position is under the control of the crew and no range designates are used. The antenna is slewed and searched all range intervals. In the auto mode, the antenna performs a spiral scan and will angle track the target as in GPC Acq. The manual mode provides only range and range rate information of a target that is in the line of sight of the antenna; there is no angle tracking performed in the manual mode. However, if the radar breaks track in auto mode, the antenna does not automatically perform a search but a search can be initiated by the crew. The GPC Acq mode is the most commonly used mode during radar operations; however, the system is switched to the Auto steering mode during vehicle maneuvers to prevent unexpected scans.

Search Modes and Signal Processing

Two types of detection modes are employed in the search process: single pulse detection (SPF) and constant false rate (CFAR). The waveform, as shown in Figure 2, is formed into data cycles with each cycle consists of a total of 85 pulse repetition intervals (PRIs). Although only 16 pulses are transmitted for each frequency, 17 pulse repetition intervals (PRIs) are allotted to allow for radar to change from one frequency to the next during the first PRI [2].

Figure 2. The Search Waveform.

1. Single Pulse Detection

Single pulse detection (SPD) mode is utilized when the designated range is less than 2552 feet. Pulse duration for SPD is 122 nsec long. After each pulse is transmitted, the duplexer switches the antenna to the receiver and the return echo from the sum channel is translated to an intermediate frequency (IF) by mixing with a local oscillator source derived from the exciter in the DA. As illustrated in Figure 3, the 78 MHz second IF signal is applied to the EA-2 radar processor where it splits into in-phase (I) and quadrature-phase (Q) components. These signals are then passed through a pair of 4 MHz video filters before being digitized by two analog-to-digital (A/D) converters. The digital data is then examined by a comparator and when the magnitude of any sample from either the I or Q components crosses the predetermined threshold, the radar will declare a hit. Target detection will be confirmed once 5 hits are received. Range to the target is estimated based on the elapsed time between the transmitted pulse and the time the detection is received.

In the cases where no designated range is used, search is initiated using SPD and if target is not detected at short range, the system will perform a long range search using CFAR as discussed in the next section.

Figure 3. Flow Diagram of Single Pulse Detection.

2. Constant False Alarm Rate

A flow diagram of CFAR detector is illustrated in Figure 4. The return signal is down converted to a video signal, splits into I and Q components, and then converted to digital data as in SPD. Unlike SPD where a sample is periodically taken and examined immediately by a comparator, the sample timing in CFAR is adjusted so that multiple digitized data are sampled by two period intervals. These intervals are known as early and late range gates which are formed overlapping about the designated range as shown in Figure 5. The timing of these gates are made equal to $3/2$ times the pulsewidth. The reason for performing multiple samples for each range gate is because

Figure 4. Flow Diagram of CFAR.

the pulsewidth length in CFAR is dependent on the designated range. And since the transmitter uses only a pulsewidth of only $2.075 \mu\text{sec}$ for ranges beyond 2552 ft, the receive signal processor employs what is known as a presummer process to integrate all the samples together to equivalently yield a longer pulsewidth. More energy, hence longer pulsewidth, is required to search a target at longer range and thus higher number of samples are taken. Magnitude of these samples from the I signal are then added together to produce a single value for the I component and the same process is done for the Q samples. Thus, for each frequency, 16 transmitted pulses result in a total of 16 pairs of I and Q values stored for each range gate.

Figure 5. CFAR Search Range Gates When Designated Range is Used.

The next step in CFAR process is to setup a bank of doppler filters. Discrete Fourier transform (DFT) is implemented for each gate to form 16 filters that span from 0 Hz to PRF Hz. Thus, each filter has a narrow band of frequencies that spreads $\text{PRF}/16$ Hz apart. The DFT process is done using 16 pairs of I & Q values from the presummer and separately integrating them in such a way that if the frequency of these samples falls within a band of a filter, the magnitude of these samples will add up in that filter but tend to cancel out in other filters. Note that an advantage of forming the doppler

filter bank is that by identifying which filter the magnitude of these samples add up, doppler frequency (hence target range rate) can be obtained. Furthermore, the DFT technique in integrating all 16 pulses resulted in a gain that reduces down the required signal-to-noise ratio. Following the doppler filter bank, the magnitude for each filter is calculated by taking the square root of the sum of the square of in-phase and square of the quadrature-phase components, i.e.

$\sqrt{I^2 + Q^2}$. The same sequence just discussed above is then applied to the next 4 frequencies. Hence, at the end of this process, there will be 5 sets of 16 filter outputs for the early gate and another 5 sets of 16 filter outputs for the late gate. At this time, the post detection integrator (PDI) will non-coherently integrate all filter outputs over the 5 frequencies. Finally the average noise level is formed by summing all filter outputs from both early and late gates and dividing by the total number of filters. The output of each filter is then compared to this noise level and target detection will be declared if any filter contains signal magnitude that is 8.5 dB higher than the average noise level.

When no designated range is used, signal processing is almost the same as with designated range except four range gates are formed as shown in figure 6 to search the entire range from 0.5 to 21.5 nautical miles.

Figure 6. CFAR Search Range Gates When No Designated Range Is Used.

Track Mode and Signal Processing

The Ku-Band radar operation is switched to the track mode upon target detection. As shown in Figure 7, track waveform is 4 times longer than the search waveform, consisting of a total of sixty four pulses for each frequency. Four time slots are allotted for these pulses where the first two are assigned for alpha and the last two are for beta measurements. Note that track mode requires the process of both the sum signal from the main antenna and the alpha and beta signals from the difference feed network. Since the EA-2 is only a single channel processor, alpha and beta signals are multiplexed onto the sum signal to produce the following signals: $\Sigma + \Delta_{\alpha}$, $\Sigma - \Delta_{\alpha}$, $\Sigma + \Delta_{\beta}$, $\Sigma - \Delta_{\beta}$.

Figure 7. The Track Waveform.

Signal processing in track also involves the presummer, doppler filtering, magnitude detection, and PDI. However, PDI is not performed on all of the filters as in search. Only 5 filters are processed including the middle filter (f_m) which contains the strongest signal and the two adjacent filters on each side (f_{m-1} , f_{m-2} , and f_{m+1} , f_{m+2}).

Range Processing

There are several steps involved in the range tracking algorithm to accurately determine the target range and provide an estimate of the predicted range for the next measurement. For each data cycle, an early gate and a late gate are formed at the predicted range, a technique that is often known as the split gate tracker. Post detection integration involves summing the outputs of the 5 tracking filters over the 5 frequencies and over the 4 time slots. After PDI, only the middle frequency f_m is used to generate the range discriminant error. The error is formed by comparing the late gate output with the early gate output. If the target is at the predicted range, energy is equally split between the two range gates and the discriminant error will be 0. However, if the target is not at the predicted range, there will be an energy offset between the two gates. More energy will appear in the early gate if the range is closer than expected and less energy will be present if the actual range is further out. Range to the target can then be obtained by adjusting the early and late gate position until energy from the two gates are equal. The next step is to get a rough estimate of the range rate by taking the range difference between this data cycle and the previous cycle. Range rate is then added to the current range measurement to obtain the predicted range for the next data cycle.

Range Rate Processing

Post detection integration in range rate processing is similar to PDI in range processing except with an additional step. Signal in the early gate is added to the late gate for each of the 5 filters.

Output from filter f_{m+1} is then compared with filter f_{m-1} to form the range rate discriminant error. If the error is 0, doppler frequency return from the target is exactly at the center frequency of filter f_m . Otherwise, range rate measurement is calculated by adding the discriminant error to the estimated range rate.

Angle Processing

Post detection integration in angle processing requires integration of 5 filters over the 5 frequencies and integration over the 2 range gates. Following PDI, outputs from the first time slot of the middle filter $f_m (\Sigma + \Delta_\alpha)$ is compared with output from the second time slot $(\Sigma - \Delta_\alpha)$ for alpha discriminant error. For beta discriminant error, outputs from the third time slot $(\Sigma + \Delta_\beta)$ of f_m is compared with the fourth time slot $(\Sigma - \Delta_\beta)$. These alpha and beta discriminant errors are then fed back to the servo system for closed loop angle tracking.

Summary

The function of the Ku-Band radar is to accurately measure and provide target information to the navigation system during rendezvous or deployment mission. A search is implemented to determine if a target is within a field of view. Either SPD or CFAR mode is called during search depending on the designated range. Short range searching will use SPD whereas CFAR is for long range searching. Once the system establishes target track, the return signal is processed by the presummer, Doppler filtering, magnitude detection, and post detection integration. The outputs from the filters are further processed by three algorithms to determine the range, range rate, and angle measurements. These measurements are used by the on-board navigation to ensure safe and fuel efficient rendezvous, satellite deployment and proximity operations.

References

- [1] Rockwell International, "Integrated Communications and Radar Equipment," Specification Document MC409-0025 Revision D, December 16, 1982.
- [2] R. S. Austin and J. G. Dodds, "Shuttle Ku-Band Radar Description and Performance Analysis," Axiomatix Report No. R8805-01, Volume I and II, November 30, 1988.